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Manufacturing and Improvement of Springbacked Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Sandwich Structures

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Introduction

HYUNDAI RM15 Concept

- HLBS = Hybrid Lightweight Body Structure (Aluminum Space Frame with CFRP)
- Integrated Sub-frame (Front & Rear)
- WRC inspired Rear Roll Cage

[1]

[3]

[4]

[5]

□ Springback phenomenon

Plenty contact points of fibers
 ↓
 Residual stress during molding
 ↓
 Stress release (Re-heated)
 ↓
 Out of plane expansion

Springback process [2]

CFRTP sandwich

Springback ratio (short for SB): the thickness changed during the heating process

[1] Bhargav S, Lightweighting lies heavy on automotive industry, Corporate, cover story, June 6, 2017.

[2] Y. Wan and J. Takahashi, "Deconsolidation behavior of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics," Journal of reinforced plastics & composites, vol13, No. 17, pp. 1613-1624, 2014.

[3] <http://aerospaceengineeringblog.com/sandwich-panel/>

[4] https://www.alibaba.com/photo-detail/More-Light-Weight-Carbon-Fiber-Sandwich_60606822697.html

[5] https://www.researchgate.net/figure/278155994_fig2_Fig-2-a-Carbon-fiber-composite-pyramidal-truss-core-sandwich-panel-b-Pyramidal

Materials and experiment

Skin: CF/PA6 UD sheet (Unidirectional carbon fiber sheet)
Thickness: 132 μm

Core: CWT (Carbon fiber card web reinforced)
 $V_f : 20\%$

Molding method

E1: One PA6 film for each CWT sheet
C2: Two PA6 films between skin and core
265°C: Molding temperature

Static mechanical properties

[1]

$$\rho \approx 0.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$$

[2]

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[1] <https://www.boatsandoutboards.co.uk/Sports-Ribs-for-sale/zodiac-pro-5-5/213036>.

[2] <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/next-generation-composite-flexible-risers-resetting-equation-matucci>.

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